

Emotional Intelligence in Media and Communication

Asst. Prof. C. A. Kharat

Dept. of English, Sau. Sushilamai Kale Arts, Commerce and Science College, Gautamnagar

Corresponding Author – Asst. Prof. C. A. Kharat

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Abstract:

Emotional Intelligence is a new concept which was invented by an American psychologists, John D. Mayer and Peter Salovey and was used in Mayer's writing in 1990. It is also known as Emotional Quotient (EQ). It is the ability to recognize, understand the emotions and feelings of our own and other people and to manage, respond and behave accordingly. It plays a vital role in media and communication.

Keywords: *Emotional Intelligence, Emotional Quotient, Communication, Media, Communal Peace, Platforms, Emotional Quotient, Navigation, etc.*

Introduction:

The two professors, John D. Mayer and Peter Salovey viewed Emotional Intelligence as the cognitive abilities that involves perceiving emotions, using emotions, understanding and monitoring one's own and other's feelings and emotions. They viewed it, mental ability rather than personality traits. E.I. in media involves leveraging empathy, self-awareness and emotion management to foster authentic engagement. It is critical for navigating social media risks and tailoring content for maximum impact. E. I in communication involves effective communication, connecting with people, to cope up with problems and thinking of solutions, developing people's skills and to handle mistakes.

Emotional Intelligence in Media:

With millions of people networking, sharing, and talking across numerous platforms, understanding and controlling emotions is critical for both personal well-being and communal peace. Social Media has transformed how we connect, communicate and view the world. Platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and TikTok have been incorporated into our lives,

changing our ideas, influencing our decisions and even affecting our emotions. It surely strengthens interpersonal communication, maintains social relationships and alleviate anxiety. However, when we use online social media to fulfill psychological needs, it may lead to problematic use. If an individual chats on social media such as WeChat, QQ, Tik Tok, Weibo and other social networking services, can lead to addiction-like symptoms. We are assaulted with emotional triggers such as continuous posts, critical remarks or a fear of missing out which can have an emotional impact on our mental health.

Emotional Intelligence, since is the capacity to identify, comprehend and control ours and others' emotions. Daniel Goleman's work has outlined five main areas of this intelligence. They are, self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and good communication that is social skills essential in this digital era. Self-awareness, being the part of EI, is essential for identifying and understanding our emotions and how they influence our ideas and behaviors.

Self-regulation is necessary to control impulses, manage stress and regulate emotional reactions in debates.

Empathy is essential for building meaningful interactions and overcoming digital differences.

Emotional Intelligence in Communication:

Emotional Intelligence is essential for both professional as well as academic success where communication is important. It is used for internal evaluation. It isn't accidental but rooted in timeless psychological laws and behavioral principles. Emotionally intelligent people understand that life isn't predictable. They think before speaking. They are mindful of their thoughts and guard their internal script and practice mindfulness in everyday life. While communicating, they don't react only the surface behavior, but look underneath it. They monitor habits, energy and emotional triggers. Emotionally intelligent people while communicating, don't react to every situation and emotion but choose to respond. and focus on conversation that strengthen relationships. We can improve our EI to achieve our goal in life. Emotional Intelligence is helpful to improve interpersonal relationships. A new term, Emotional Quotient has been coined to measure emotional intelligence and strong EQ skills contribute to effective communication, healthy relationships and navigating and complex situations. Emotional Intelligence can help us –

- To realize and understand our emotions and feelings and those of others in a situation and allows us to communicate with others in an effective way. By understanding and responding their emotions properly in a calm and understanding manner will certainly lead to positive outcomes and thus reduce friction. For example, when we see someone carrying a huge lump of hay, we must understand his/her feelings and should help him/her by carrying the same to a certain distance, results in mental well-being.

- By understanding ours and others' emotions, we get connected with people, can form our own teams and make more friends.
- With the help of EI, we can cope up with others, their problems and think of solutions instead of overwhelmed by problems in life, such as, sudden cancellation of a train, missing your own wallet somewhere, etc.
- EI helps us in becoming a leader of our team by understanding, motivating, inspiring the members to give their best, respond the members suggestions and feedback in a positive way. This is important for the existence and well-being of the team or group.
- EI also helps us to improve soft-skills and communication performance. Don't criticize and hurt people for their mistakes and what went wrong in a situation. Don't get furious, get curious by listening their feedback. For example, if you get furious with someone else, that person will get hurt and will not do his/her best performance.

Conclusion:

Thus, Emotional Intelligence plays an important role in both, media and communication. It has five key components or aspects such as, self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and good social skills that includes, communication skills, team-building skills, leadership skills, decision-making skills, problem-solving skills etc. which are essential in this digital era. It helps us to communicate with others in an effective way such as-to understand people, get connected with them, to cope up with them and understand their problems and think of solutions, to motivate, and inspire the members to give their best etc. It also helps us to improve our soft-skills and communication performance

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